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**UNIVERSITY
OF ABERDEEN**

School of Law

**NIGERIA'S OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIME, SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT AND THE PETROLEUM INDUSTRY ACT 2021:
LESSONS TO BE LEARNED FROM THE UNITED KINGDOM AND THE
UNITED STATES OF AMERICA**

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Abstract

In view of global strides towards achieving sustainable development, this study assesses the robustness of Nigeria's offshore safety regime, especially considering Nigeria's Petroleum Industry Act 2021. This assessment is substantiated by comparative case studies of the safety regimes in the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States of America (US). Beginning in chapter one, this study establishes the relationship between occupational safety and health and sustainable development. Following which the regulatory regimes of Nigeria, UK and US are explored individually. In chapter 2, the study expounds Nigeria's regime revealing its legislative framework, regulatory bodies and regulatory orientation. Importantly, this chapter explores Nigeria's newly enacted Petroleum Industry Act 2021. This Act replaces the longstanding Petroleum Act 1969, and has as one its objectives, the achievement of the sustainable development of its petroleum resources. The impact of this Act on Nigeria's regime will therefore be assessed. This study goes on to elucidate the offshore safety regimes of UK and US in chapter 3. The theoretical overview of these jurisdictions serves as the basis for the comparative analysis carried out in chapter 4. In chapter 4, therefore, the similarities and differences of these three jurisdictions are highlighted with a view to exposing the strengths and weaknesses of Nigeria's regime, particularly as established by the new Petroleum Industry Act. This will highlight areas in Nigeria's regime that should be improved. The advantages of a safe offshore safety regime cannot be overemphasised. The recent disaster on Nigeria's Continental Shelf in February 2022 serves as a justifiable reminder that offshore safety is a current matter of national interest which must be continuously enhanced to keep up with the unpredictable offshore environment and safeguard the lives of the people working there. Needless to say, an industry cannot achieve sustainable development if it threatens the lives, health and security of its workers. Ultimately, chapter 5 concludes this study by proposing recommendations in line with the disclosures unveiled in chapter 4.

TABLE OF CONTENT

TITLE PAGE	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	ii
ABSTRACT	iii
TABLE OF CONTENT	iv
CHAPTER 1 – GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 BACKGROUND OF RESEARCH.....	1
1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT	1
1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS	2
1.4 SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF RESEARCH.....	3
1.5 METHODOLOGY	3
1.6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	4
CHAPTER 2 – OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIME OF NIGERIA	7
2.1 INTRODUCTION.....	7
2.2 LEGAL FRAMEWORK	8
2.2.1 THE CONSTITUTION OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA 1999 (AS AMENDED).....	8
2.2.2 PETROLEUM INDUSTRY ACT 2021	9
2.2.3 MINERAL OILS (SAFETY) REGULATIONS 1997.....	10
2.2.4 PETROLEUM (DRILLING AND PRODUCTION) REGULATIONS 1969.....	11
2.3 REGULATORY AUTHORITY	12
2.3.1 NIGERIAN UPSTREAM PETROLEUM REGULATORY COMMISSION	13
2.4 CONCLUSION	13
CHAPTER 3 – THE OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIMES OF THE UNITED KINGDOM AND THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	14
3.1 INTRODUCTION.....	14
3.2 OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIME OF THE UNITED KINGDOM	14
3.2.1 EARLY PHASE	14
3.2.2 THE ROBENS COMMITTEE	15

3.2.3	THE BURGOYNE COMMITTEE.....	16
3.2.4	THE PIPER ALPHA DISASTER AND LORD CULLEN’S REPORT	16
3.2.5	SAFETY CASE APPROACH.....	17
3.2.6	THE OFFSHORE INSTALLATIONS (OFFSHORE SAFETY DIRECTIVE) (SAFETY CASE ETC.) REGULATIONS 2015.....	17
3.3	OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIME OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	19
3.3.1	PRE-MACONDO DISASTER	19
3.3.2	MACONDO DISASTER.....	20
3.3.3	MACONDO DISASTER INVESTIGATIONS.....	20
3.3.4	POST-MACONDO DISASTER REGULATORY REFORM	22
3.4	CONCLUSION	23

CHAPTER 4 – COMPARATIVE CASE STUDIES OF THE OFFSHORE REGIMES OF NIGERIA, UK AND US 24

4.1	INTRODUCTION.....	24
4.2	LEGAL FRAMEWORKS AND REGULATORY APPROACHES	24
4.3	REGULATORY BODIES.....	27
4.4	SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND WORKFORCE INVOLVEMENT.....	28
4.5	CONCLUSION	31

CHAPTER 5 – CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS 32

5.1	CONCLUSION	32
5.2	RECOMMENDATIONS	33

BIBLIOGRAPHY 34

1. CHAPTER 1 – GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Research

Despite the world's shift towards renewable energy, the significance of oil and gas in various economies of the world cannot be denied. For Nigeria especially, oil and gas comprise almost 90% of its revenues.¹ However, the offshore petroleum industry, though lucrative, exposes workers to one of the toughest environments.² In fact, the words 'dangerous, arduous and socially isolating'³ have been used to describe the offshore environment. While much attention is paid to the revenues the industry accrues, some attention is given to the environment which suffers from the oil spills that occur during exploitation. Little attention, however, is given to the safety of workers who spend months in the hostile and hazardous environment. According to KPMG, although Nigeria is plagued by regulatory and security risks, it still boasts of her rich and lucrative offshore petroleum resources.⁴

With the enactment of the Petroleum Industry Act 2021, Nigeria seeks to achieve the sustainable development of the industry. But the concept of sustainable development is wider than many perceive. The concept stands on the three pillars of economy (revenues from petroleum resources), environment (the marine environment) and society (the offshore workers). Human lives are as invaluable as the environment in which they live, no longer should social sustainability be relegated. There is a role for the law to play.

Law is the foundation of offshore safety regimes. Through legal reforms, the offshore regimes of the United Kingdom and the United States of America have become safer for workers. The experiences of these countries show that the consequences of a faulty regime are calamitous and irreversible, hence, it is too risky for Nigeria to be reactive in offshore regulation.

1.2 Problem Statement

In 1995, thirteen offshore workers were killed, four went missing and others were severely injured in the explosion of a Mobil oil rig on the Nigerian Continental Shelf.⁵ Between 2010 and 2017, no less

¹ KPMG NIGERIA, 'Nigeria's Oil and Gas Industry Brief' (Amazon aws, 2014) <<https://s3.amazonaws.com/rgi-documents/807cb4d6f40af92c55d9a0cd4aed6c942cb08537.pdf>> accessed 25 July 2022

² Janice Langan-Fox and Cary L. Cooper. (eds), *Handbook of Stress in the Occupations* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2011)

³ D H Elliott, 'The offshore worker' (1985) 229(1404) *The Practitioner* < <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/offshore-worker/docview/76235907/se-2?accountid=8155>> accessed 13 July 2022

⁴ KPMG NIGERIA (n 1)

⁵ <https://apnews.com/article/e2d10e07d85b48bfb6630ff4a2a15800> Dave Gorringer, 'Identifying & Mitigating Risks – Are we really getting better?' (Crarisk.com) <<https://Identifying Mitigating Risks Oct 2014.pdf>> accessed 26 July 2022

than 308 workers died while working in the petroleum industry.⁶ Recently, in February 2022, three offshore workers were killed and four went missing at an offshore explosion of the Trinity Spirit Floating Production, Storage and Offloading (FPSO) in Warri, Nigeria.⁷ There is no record that after any of these incidents, Nigeria reassessed its safety framework. What is regularly projected as priority is the increase of Nigeria's petroleum production. Meanwhile, the inherent risks of the industry continue to evolve.⁸ This is indicative of a frail regime.

A robust safety regime is key to the sustainability of the industry, the community, and the country at large. Poor safety regimes expose offshore workers to disasters with irreversible consequences such as deaths and injuries. The Piper Alpha disaster on the UK Continental Shelf and the Macondo disaster on the US Outer Continental Shelf testify to this.

Because of the novelty of the Petroleum Industry Act 2021, there is limited literature on its impact in establishing a safer regime in Nigeria. This study therefore determines whether the Act is effective in establishing a robust regime. This will be achieved through comparative case studies of Nigeria's regime against those of the UK and the US. The lessons drawn from these regimes will underpin the recommendations proposed towards establishing a robust offshore safety regime in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between sustainable development and occupational health and safety?
2. To what extent is Nigeria's offshore safety regime robust?
3. What is the impact of the Petroleum Industry Act on Nigeria's regime?
4. What lessons can be learned by Nigeria from the offshore safety regimes of the UK and US?

⁶ Daily Trust, 'Oily but deadly: How 308 deaths haunt oil sector' (Daily Trust) <[https://The Cat \(dailytrust.com\)](https://The Cat (dailytrust.com))> accessed 12 July 2022

⁷ Emmanuel Addeh and Peter Uzoho, 'SEPCOL Explosion: More Bodies Recovered, Four Still Missing' This Day (Nigeria, 8 February 2022) <[SEPCOL Explosion: More Bodies Recovered, Four Still Missing – THISDAYLIVE](https://www.thisdaylive.com/articles/sepcol-explosion-more-bodies-recovered-four-still-missing/)> accessed 12 July 2022

⁸ Amy Jaff, James Coan, and Alexander MacDonald, 'The Risk and Regulation of Deepwater Offshore Drilling: American and Canadian Perspectives' (Wilson Centre, 2014) <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/the-risk-and-regulation-deepwater-offshore-drilling-american-and-canadian-perspectives> accessed 11 July 2022

1.4 Scope and Limitations of Research

This research focuses on legal regulation of offshore safety. Other modes of regulation such as self-regulation, co-regulation and meta-regulation are not contemplated in this work.

Current trends in the offshore safety regimes now include environmental concerns. For example, the US Safety and Environmental Management Systems (SEMS) and UK's SEMS. This is laudable. However, this study focuses on the safety aspect of offshore regulation as it relates to workers.

A key challenge in answering the research questions is the lack of public database of accidents, injuries and near misses that occur on Nigeria's Continental Shelf. Thus, it is said that Nigeria's industry is submerged in secrecy.⁹ This makes it difficult to evaluate safety trends in the industry. Likewise, the paucity of existing literature on the current regime in Nigeria is limited. Nonetheless, reference is made to sound secondary resources to buttress this study.

1.5 Methodology

This study uses doctrinal legal research and comparative methodologies to first detail the regulatory regimes of Nigeria, US, and UK, and secondly, to compare these regimes in order to assess the efficacy of Nigeria's regime.

The UK is a trailblazer in offshore regulation, although not without a precarious past. UK also shares historical and common law relations with Nigeria. Health and safety law in Nigeria generally developed from the influence of British colonialism, and the laws inherited post-independence.¹⁰ Today, the position has not changed for Nigeria that there is still so much to learn from the UK.

US, on the other hand, implemented a regulatory approach which is like Nigeria's for almost forty years, until its reform in 2010 after the Macondo disaster. The factors that necessitated this change

⁹ Chinweze Uhegbu, 'A Critical Evaluation of the offshore Safety Regulations In Nigeria: A Comparative Case Study of Norway and United Kingdom' (Master's thesis, Coventry University 2015) <https://www.academia.edu/12077381/A_CRITICAL_EVALUATION_OF_THE_OFFSHORE_SAFETY_REGULATIONS_IN_NIGERIA_A_COMPARATIVE_CASE_STUDY_OF_NORWAY_AND_UNITED_KINGDOM> accessed 14 July 2022

¹⁰ Dare Arowolo, 'The Effects of Western Civilization and Culture on Africa' (2010) 1 (1) Afro Asia Journal of Social Sciences <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266252078_The_effects_of_western_civilisation_and_culture_on_Africa> accessed 20 June 2022

are worthy considerations for Nigeria. Indeed, it is never too late to make a change in the right direction.

These two jurisdictions have suffered significant disasters in safety regulation which caused them to implement conscientious reforms towards best practice. ‘From the errors of others, a wise man corrects his own,’¹¹ it is cheaper that way.¹² Nigeria does not need to experience such calamities to determine the robustness of its regime or to be inspired to improve its regime. Learning from the experiences of other regimes has preventive advantageous.

1.6 Relationship between occupational health and safety and sustainable development.

The ILO/WHO Joint Committee on Occupational Health defines occupational safety and health as the promotion and maintenance of the highest physical, mental, and social well-being of workers.¹³ Sustainable development, on the other hand, is one of those concepts which do not enjoy a universally agreed definition. The most referenced definition, however, is that “sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”¹⁴

Sustainability is usually discussed in relation to environmental sustainability. But in early and major discourse on sustainable development, the concept is understood to comprise a threefold of social, environmental, and economic factors.¹⁵ The social aspect of sustainability is often overlooked. When sustainability strategies are being drawn up, so little, if any, considerations are given to safety.¹⁶

In 2015, the United Nations adopted 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.¹⁷ GOAL 8 titled ‘Decent Work and Economic Growth’ has the specific target to ‘protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all

¹¹ Publilius Syrus

¹² Donald J. Trump

¹³ International Labour Organisation, ‘Improving health in the workplace: ILO’s framework for action’ (ILO, 2014) <https://www.ilo.org/safework/info/publications/WCMS_329350/lang--en/index.htm> accessed 12 July 2022

¹⁴ Gro Brundtland (ed), *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future* (United Nations, Oxford University Press 1987)

¹⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁶ Kayode Fowode, ‘Occupational health and safety in sustainability and its reporting- The common mistakes’ (LinkedIn, 2019) <<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/occupational-health-safety-sustainability-its-common>> accessed 14 July 2022

¹⁷ OSHA, ‘Sustainability in the Workplace: A New Approach for Advancing Worker Safety and Health’ (elcosh, 2016) <<https://elcosh.org/document/4199/d001486/sustainability-in-the-workplace:-a-new-approach-for-advancing-worker-safety-and-health.html>> accessed 18 July 2022

workers....’ Other goals which have bearings on workers' health and safety include Goal 3 – Quality Health, and Goal 12 Sustainable Consumption and Production.¹⁸ According to World Health Organisation, decent work is the key to sustainable development.¹⁹

At the centre of both sustainability and safety is the conservation of resources. Bruntland identifies human resources as the ultimate resource.²⁰ Workplace accidents, injuries and illness occasion loss of manpower, materials, time, money in compensating victims and their families and thus, increases cost of production and reducing the profit margin of the organisation and overall GDP of the country.²¹ In fact, the International Labour Organization estimated that 4% of global GDP is lost due to work accidents and diseases.²²

On the contrary, the prevention of accidents and injuries at work and the protection of workers from physical and psychological harm requires the conservative use of resources which minimise unnecessary loss of human and material resources.²³ Safe and healthy workers facilitate effective productivity and enhance product quality which avoids unnecessary energy and material losses.²⁴ The International Social Security Association (ISSA) estimated that every euro invested in OSH sees a return of €2.20.²⁵ A healthy workforce is, thus, the main agent for socioeconomic development.²⁶ Also, it is shown that environmental health risks are usually first detected in the workplace or among the working population.²⁷ As a result, a safe work environment is a viable tool for environmental health risks prevention.²⁸

If sustainable development is economic growth that is both socially and environmentally sustainable,²⁹ it should, therefore, not be second-guessed whether occupational safety is at the heart

¹⁸ Cristina Reis and others, “Occupational Health and Safety-Sustainable Development and the Changes in Organizations” In *Occupational and Environmental Safety and Health II* (Springer International Publishing 2020) 67

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Bruntland (n 14)

²¹ Olatubi Matthew Idowu and Olatubi Victoria Iyabo, ‘Ensuring a Safe Working Environment in Nigeria: Reality or Myth’ (2017) 2(3) *American Journal of Environmental and Resource Economics*

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325381991_Ensuring_a_Safe_Working_Environment_in_Nigeria_Reality_or_Myth> accessed 14 July 2022

²² Reis (n 18)

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ IOSH, ‘Harnessing the Power of Social Sustainability’ (iosh, 2018) <<https://iosh.com/businesses/iosh-for-business/catch-the-wave/sustainability/>> accessed 18 July 2022

²⁶ *ibid.*

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ *ibid.*

²⁹ Bruntland (n 14)

of sustainable development.³⁰ No organisation, endeavour, industry can truly be sustainable if its working practices are unsafe for its workers.³¹ According to U.S. Occupational Safety and Health Administration, ‘A building, no matter how energy efficient or healthy for occupants, is not sustainable if a construction worker is killed while building it. Furniture, no matter how responsibly the wood is harvested, is not sustainable if a woodworker loses a limb during manufacturing...’³² Every person, including workers in the offshore petroleum industry, ‘has the right to health, which is defined by WHO as a state of complete physical and mental wellbeing and not only the absence of disease and infirmity.’³³ True sustainability prioritises human resources through safety considerations.

Safety is truly a foundation for sustainable growth.³⁴

DIAGRAMS ILLUSTRATING THE THREE-DIMENSIONAL SUSTAIBILITY

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³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ IOSH (n 25)

³² OSHA (n 17)

³³ Maria Neira, ‘Improving Health in the Workplace: ILO’s Framework for Action’ (ILO, 2014) <https://www.ilo.org/safework/info/publications/WCMS_329350/lang--en/index.htm> accessed 12 July 2022

³⁴ Mike Taubitz, ‘How Safety Fits with Sustainability’ (OSH, 2010) <<https://ohsonline.com/articles/2010/09/01/how-safety-fits-with-sustainability.aspx?m=1>> accessed 18 July 2022

³⁵ OSHA (n 17)

³⁶ Thwink.org, ‘The Three Pillars of Sustainability’ (Thwink.org) <<https://www.thwink.org/sustain/glossary/ThreePillarsOfSustainability.htm>> accessed 18 July 2022

2. CHAPTER 2 - OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIME OF NIGERIA

2.1 Introduction

Nigeria is commonly referred to as the giant of Africa³⁷ for reasons including that Nigeria has the largest population,³⁸ the 14th largest land mass,³⁹ and emerges as the largest oil producing country,⁴⁰ ranking 15th globally.⁴¹ Since the beginning of oil exploration in Nigeria in 1903,⁴² and its eventual discovery about half a century later by Shell-BP at Oloibiri in the Niger Delta in 1956, the industry has continued to expand.⁴³ At that time, Shell-BP was a sole concessionaire.⁴⁴ The history of oil exploration and discovery in Nigeria is a lengthy voyage not embarked on in this study.

It is worthy to note, however, that Nigeria joined the league of oil producing and exporting countries in 1958.⁴⁵ In 1971, Nigeria became a member of the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC).⁴⁶ Nigeria's petroleum industry makes for about eight(8) percent of Nigeria's GDP and almost ninety (90) percent of all her export value.⁴⁷ In 2021, Nigeria's average daily oil production was about 1.6 million barrels per day.⁴⁸ Nigeria's oil is light and low in sulphuric content and thus, attractive to foreign countries.⁴⁹ With other factors, this makes Nigeria the ninth largest oil exporter

³⁷ Itibari M. Zulu, 'Nigeria: the Giant of Africa' (2009) 3(3) Journal of Pan African Studies <<https://Nigeria: the Giant of Africa>> 2 August 2022.

³⁸ The World Bank, 'Population, total' (The World Bank, 2022) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?most_recent_value_desc=true> accessed 26 July 2022

³⁹ International Labour Organisation, 'Nigeria Country Profile on Occupational Safety and Health' (International Labour Organisation, 2016) <https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---africa/---ro-abidjan/---ilo-abuja/documents/publication/wcms_552748.pdf> accessed 18 July 2022

⁴⁰ Doris Dokua Sasu, 'Oil industry in Nigeria - statistics & facts' (Statista, 5 April 2022) <<https://www.statista.com/oil-industry-in-nigeria/>> accessed 18 July 2022

⁴¹ Bp, 'bp Statistical Review of World Energy' (bp, 2021) <<https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2021-full-report.pdf>> accessed 25 July 2022

⁴² By two companies, Nigeria Properties (Limited) and the Nigeria and West African Development Syndicate (Limited). See Phia Steyn, 'Oil Exploration in Colonial Nigeria c. 1903–58' (2009) 37(2) Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History <<https://www.africabib.org/http.php?RID=A00003030>> accessed 15 July 2022

⁴³ ibid

⁴⁴ ibid

⁴⁵ ibid

⁴⁶ Mohammad Barkindo, 'Nigeria and OPEC: 50 years together' (OPEC, 2021) <<https://Nigeria and OPEC/>> accessed 20 July 2022

⁴⁷ Sasu (n 40)

⁴⁸ ibid

⁴⁹ Bassam Fattouh and Adi Imsirovic, 'Nigerian Barrels and the Demand Shock: Differentials and Changing Oil Trade Flows' (Oxford Energy, July 2020) <<https://www.oxfordenergy.org/publications/nigerian-barrels-and-the-demand-shock-differentials-and-changing-oil-trade-flows/>> accessed 2 August 2022

in the world in terms of value.⁵⁰ Nigeria's exports are usually directed towards Europe and Asia.⁵¹ In the second quarter of 2021, Nigeria's crude oil export to Europe had an estimated value of 1.48 trillion Naira.^{52,53} To Asia, exports were estimated at about 1.46 trillion Naira.^{54,55} Nigeria is also a main exporter to the United States of America.⁵⁶ These, no doubt, show how much Nigeria's economy depends on its petroleum industry. Despite this glamorous profile, the offshore regime in Nigeria is allegedly fraught with regulatory challenges.⁵⁷ Whether this argument can be upheld in light of the new Petroleum Industry Act 2021 is questionable.

In this chapter, the legal regime of offshore safety in Nigeria will be explored; the laws, regulations, regulatory authorities, model as well as the impact of the new Petroleum Industry Act 2021. This overview will serve in the comparative analysis between Nigeria's regime and those of other jurisdictions considered in the following chapter.

2.2 Legal Framework

Legal provisions for offshore safety in Nigeria are dispersed in different laws including the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended; the Petroleum Industry Act 2021; the Petroleum (Drilling and Production) Regulations 1969; the Mineral Oils (Safety) Regulations 1997 and the Guidelines pursuant to these regulations.

2.2.1 The Constitution of The Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria⁵⁸ (the 'Constitution') is the highest law in Nigeria. All other legal instruments and powers derive authority from the Constitution.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Sasu (n 40)

⁵² *ibid.*

⁵³ Equivalent to about £2,907,965,316.40, \$3,554,274,612.00

⁵⁴ Sasu (n 40)

⁵⁵ Equivalent to about £2,868,387,988.22, \$3,506,243,874.00

⁵⁶ Sasu (n 40)

⁵⁷ KPMG NIGERIA (n 1)

⁵⁸ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) as amended Cap. C.23, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 (Constitution)

Section 17 of the Constitution states that in furtherance of social order, human sanctity and dignity shall be recognised, maintained and enhanced, and the exploitation of human and natural resources for reasons other than the good of the community shall be prevented.⁵⁹ The Constitution also requires the government to direct its policy towards ensuring that conditions of work are just and humane; and that the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are protected and not endangered or abused.⁶⁰ Although these parts of the Constitution⁶¹ are unenforceable due to their non-justiciable character, it remains the responsibility of the government to observe them.⁶² Nonetheless, the enforceable fundamental human rights guarantee the right of every citizen to dignity of labour.⁶³

The Constitution vests law-making powers concerning occupational health, welfare and conditions exclusively on the National Assembly at federal level.⁶⁴ It also vests exclusive jurisdiction on the National Industrial Court to try civil matters relating to the “...health, safety and welfare of labour, employee, workers and related matters.”⁶⁵

The Constitution, therefore, is the bedrock of safety regulation in the country.

2.2.2 Petroleum Industry Act 2021⁶⁶

The Petroleum Industry Act 2021 (the ‘PIA’) repealed the long-standing Petroleum Act, 1969⁶⁷ (the ‘PA’) by its passing in August 2021.⁶⁸

Like its predecessor, PIA vests entire ownership and control in the state of all petroleum in, under or upon any land. This position received judicial assent from the highest court in Nigeria, the Supreme Court.⁶⁹ Nevertheless, the Minister of Petroleum Resources is empowered to grant some rights to companies to explore, prospect and mine oil through licences.⁷⁰

⁵⁹ Constitution, ss 17(b) and (d)

⁶⁰ Constitution, ss 17(3) (a-h)

⁶¹ Constitution, Chapter II titled Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy

⁶² Constitution, s 13

⁶³ Constitution, s 31

⁶⁴ Constitution, sch 2, Item 34

⁶⁵ Section 254C of the Constitution of The Federal Republic of Nigeria (Third Alteration) Act, 2010 Act. No. 3

⁶⁶ Petroleum Industry Act 2021 LFN 2004 (Petroleum Industry Act)

⁶⁷ Petroleum Act CAP P10 (Chapter 350) LFN 1990 (Petroleum Act)

⁶⁸ Morgan Lewis, ‘Nigeria Overhauls Its Oil and Gas Laws With Petroleum Industry Act’ (Morgan Lewis, 14 December 2021) <<https://www.morganlewis.com/pubs/2021/12/nigeria-overhauls-its-oil-and-gas-laws-with-petroleum-industry-act>> accessed 15 July 2022

⁶⁹ Attorney General of the Federation v Attorney General of Abia State [2002] 4 NSCC 51 (Nigeria).

⁷⁰ Petroleum Industry Act, s 3(g)

The PIA does not provide directly for the safety of offshore workers. Rather, it empowers the Minister to formulate government policy for the industry.⁷¹ It also empowers the offshore regulator to issue regulations for offshore safety.⁷² Since its passing, no regulations have been issued. Instead, it saves⁷³ regulations issued under section 9 of the PA which empowered the Minister to make regulations concerning safe working,⁷⁴ the reporting of accidents,⁷⁵ inquiries into accidents,⁷⁶ construction and maintenance operations.⁷⁷ Although this section is not replicated in the PIA, the regulations issued under it remain in force as discussed below.

2.2.3 Mineral Oils (Safety) Regulations 1997⁷⁸

The Mineral Oils (Safety) Regulations 1997 (the ‘MOSRegulations’) were issued pursuant to the PA but are saved by the PIA and remain in force *mutatis mutandis* as if they were issued by the Authority established by the PIA, and until they are replaced, repealed or revoked.

The MOSRegulations contain 5 chapters viz Part I – Duties of licensees and lessees; Part ii – Duties of managers; Part III – Duties of Employees; Part IV – Diving Operations; and Part V – Miscellaneous. As these titles suggest, these chapters prescribe detailed responsibilities which must be complied with by the respective parties, failure of which amounts to offences punishable by fine and/or imprisonment. For example, licensees and lessees are to ensure that personal protective equipment are used and maintained well; that comprehensive and safe operational guidelines and procedures are provided for workers; and that health promotion programmes are developed for workers. Their failure to comply is punishable by a fine not exceeding N250,000⁷⁹ and/or imprisonment not exceeding 5 years.⁸⁰ The responsibilities of managers⁸¹ and employees⁸² are similar long lists of mandatory duties and accompanying penalties for non-compliance.

Additionally, the regulations mandate good oil field practice in accordance with the appropriate current Institute of Petroleum Safety Codes; the American Petroleum Institute Codes; the American

⁷¹ Petroleum Industry Act, s 3(1)(a)

⁷² Petroleum Industry Act, s 216

⁷³ Petroleum Industry Act, s 311

⁷⁴ Petroleum Act, s 9(1)(b)(i)

⁷⁵ Petroleum Act, s 9(1)(b)(iv)

⁷⁶ Petroleum Act, s 9(1)(b)(v)

⁷⁷ Petroleum Act, ss 9(1)(c) and (d)

⁷⁸ The Mineral Oils (Safety) Regulations 1997 CAP 350 LFN 2004 (MOSRegulations)

⁷⁹ Equivalent to about £491.38, \$600.38

⁸⁰ MOSRegulations, pt I

⁸¹ MOSRegulations, pt II

⁸² MOSRegulations, pt III

Society of Mechanical Engineers Codes; or any other internationally recognised and accepted systems.⁸³

2.2.4 Petroleum (Drilling and Production) Regulations 1969⁸⁴

Like the MOS Regulations, the Petroleum (Drilling and Production) Regulations 1969 (the ‘PDR Regulations’) were saved by the PIA.⁸⁵

Regulation 45 vests a broad obligation on licensees and lessees to comply with safety regulations and instruments. Other provisions relating to OHS are indirect and relate only insofar as they require licensees and lessees to construct installations to ensure safe navigation,⁸⁶ maintain boreholes, wells, apparatus and appliances; and to conduct operations properly and in accordance with acceptable methods and good oil field practice.⁸⁷

Guidelines are issued pursuant to these regulations and are, likewise, saved by the PIA.⁸⁸ Most important of these guidelines to this study are the Safety Case Guidelines 2020 which establishes the safety case approach in Nigeria.⁸⁹ These Guidelines are influenced by Lord Cullen’s recommendation for the United Kingdom’s safety regime.⁹⁰ Its section 4 lists the contents of a safety case and this includes details of the operator’s safety management system. Operators are, therefore, required to develop a safety case and implement safety management systems as a form of internal control.⁹¹ The safety case must show that employees and regulators participated in its development.⁹² The safety case is to be submitted,⁹³ reviewed,⁹⁴ approved⁹⁵ and verified⁹⁶ by the regulator. It is expected to be

⁸³ MOS Regulations, pt II

⁸⁴ Petroleum (Drilling and Production) Regulations 1969 L.N. 69 of 1969 (PDR Regulations)

⁸⁵ Petroleum Industry Act, s 311

⁸⁶ PDR Regulations, reg 24

⁸⁷ PDR Regulations, reg 37

⁸⁸ Guidelines and Procedure for Travel to Offshore/Swamp Location and Obtainment of Offshore Safety Permit 2020; Guidelines for Compliance with the Technical Safety Control (TSC) Requirements 2020; Guidelines for The Implementation of Risk Based Inspection in The Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry 2020; Guidelines and Procedure for Lifting Equipment and Lifting Operations 2020; Guidelines & Procedure for Construction Operation & Maintenance of Pipelines 2020.

⁸⁹ Safety Case Guidelines for Oil and Gas Facilities in Nigeria 2020 (Guidelines)

⁹⁰ Guidelines, s 1.1

⁹¹ Guidelines, s 4.5

⁹² Guidelines, s 5.4

⁹³ Guidelines, s 5.2

⁹⁴ Guidelines, s 5.3

⁹⁵ *ibid*

⁹⁶ Guidelines, s 5.4

a living document, revised and kept up to date.⁹⁷ The safety case is to be resubmitted for approval every five (5) years.⁹⁸

2.3 Regulatory Authority

The regulator of the offshore petroleum industry in Nigeria has had a checkered history. The unstable political regime characterised by several coups, the prevalence of corruption, lack of independence, lack of accountability and transparency contributed to this.⁹⁹ Two regulators which eventually stood the test of time were the Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC) and the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR).¹⁰⁰ NNPC was established in 1977 to manage Nigeria's interest in petroleum resources¹⁰¹ as the state's Oil Company, having participatory government shares in all licenses issued by the Minister under the Petroleum Act.¹⁰² NNPC engaged in commercial petroleum activities and regulated safety through its subsidiary, DPR.¹⁰³ The Minister which was the head of the Ministry of Petroleum Resources and the chairman of the board of NNPC, exercised its powers through these bodies.¹⁰⁴ DPR as safety regulator, therefore, lacked independence and suffered conflicting interests of revenue maximisation and safety regulation.¹⁰⁵

Since the passing of PIA, these regulators ceased to exist. The PIA established the Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPC Limited)¹⁰⁶ as a private limited liability company, an independent commercial entity, and a concessionaire under all production sharing contracts, profit

⁹⁷ Guidelines, s 6

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Musikilu Mojeed 'Monumental Oil Subsidy Fraud And Corruption at the NNPC-The Damning KPMG Report: Premium Times' (Sahara Reporters, 2011) <<https://saharareporters.com/2011/12/09/monumental-oil-subsidy-fraud-and-corruption-nnpc-damning-kpmg-report-premium-times>> accessed 18 July 2022

¹⁰⁰ They have both existed since the 1970s till 2021.

¹⁰¹ Olusola John Jegede and Winifred Idiaru, 'Nigeria: Legal Framework And Requirements For Oil And Gas Investment In Nigeria' (Mondaq, 2020) <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/oil-gas-electricity/998566/legal-framework-and-requirements-for-oil-and-gas-investment-in-nigeria>> accessed 20 July 2022

¹⁰² The Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Act 2004, s 1

¹⁰³ Ugo Nwokeji, 'The Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation and the Development of The Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry: History, Strategies and Current Directions' (2007) The James A. Baker III Institute For Public Policy, Rice University <https://www.bakerinstitute.org/media/files/page/9b067dc6/noc_nnpc_ugo.pdf> accessed 18 July 2022

¹⁰⁴ ibid

¹⁰⁵ ibid.

¹⁰⁶ Petroleum Industry Act, s 53

sharing, and risk sharing contracts on behalf of Nigeria.¹⁰⁷ The PIA also established the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission.¹⁰⁸

2.3.1 Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission

The Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission ('NUPRC') replaces DPR to ensure that safety regulations conform with best practices.¹⁰⁹ NUPRC has the objectives to 'ensure that upstream operations are carried out in a manner to minimise waste and achieve optimal government revenues'¹¹⁰ and 'to promote health, safe, efficient and effective conduct of upstream operations in an environmentally friendly and sustainable manner.'¹¹¹ This structure still bears much semblance with what was obtainable before the PIA. The establishment of a new regulators appears to merely be effective in having different regulators for the upstream and downstream industries.

2.4 Conclusion

This chapter explored the regime of offshore safety in Nigeria. It began by recognising the Constitution as the basis of the regulatory regime and went on to discuss the laws enacted pursuant to it.

The Petroleum Industry Act 2021 was identified as the primary legislation relevant to offshore safety. The changes introduced to the regime by the Act, such as the establishment of a new regulator, were highlighted.

This chapter also discussed the relevant regulations pursuant to the act which are the Minerals Oil (Safety) Regulations and the Petroleum (Drilling and Operation) Regulations. These regulations are prescriptive and adopt a command-and-control model. The Safety Case Guidelines, however, introduce performance-based elements. Thus, Nigeria's regime comprises elements of both prescriptive and performance-based approaches. However, the overall regime is largely prescriptive.

Beginning with a brief history of past regulators, this chapter elucidated the establishment and objectives of the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority as the authority regulating offshore safety in Nigeria.

¹⁰⁷ *ibid*

¹⁰⁸ Petroleum Industry Act, s 4

¹⁰⁹ 'Functions of NUPRC' (Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission) <<https://www.nuprc.gov.ng/functions-of-nuprc/>> accessed 18 June 2022

¹¹⁰ Petroleum Industry Act, s 6(c)

¹¹¹ Petroleum Industry Act, s 6(d)

3. CHAPTER 3 - THE OFFSHORE SAFETY REGIMES OF THE UNITED KINGDOM AND THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

3.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a theoretical overview of the offshore safety regimes of the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States of America (UK). These jurisdictions were meticulously selected for comparative purposes.

The United Kingdom Continental Shelf is considered as one of the most hostile offshore environments.¹¹² Its safety framework is also considered to be one of the most mature, having been resilient despite major setbacks over the years.¹¹³ Notably, Nigeria and UK have historical and common law relations. Also, health and safety law in Nigeria developed from the influence of British colonialism, and the laws inherited post-independence. The US, on the other hand, had for about forty years implemented a regulatory approach like Nigeria's, until its reform in 2010. What triggered this reform will be discussed in this chapter.

This overview will detail the legislative frameworks, regulatory authorities, orientations and experiences in the offshore regulation of these jurisdictions.

3.2 Offshore Safety Regime of The United Kingdom

UK has had a long history in the development of its offshore safety regime which was influenced by major disasters. This history is bifurcated accordingly.

3.2.1 Early Phase

UK's oil and gas journey burgeoned in early 1960s when natural gas was discovered in the UK Continental Shelf (UKCS).¹¹⁴ Being a period of economic downturn, UK ecstatically seized the opportunity to enact the Continental Shelf Act 1964 which permitted exploitation.¹¹⁵ UK simply replicated the onshore regulatory framework and applied it offshore.¹¹⁶ The shortcomings of this duplication were exposed when the Sea Gem rig collapsed on 27 December 1965, barely three months

¹¹² John Paterson, 'Health and Safety at Work Offshore' in Greg Gordon, John Paterson, and Emre Usenmez (eds), *Oil and Gas Law: Current Practice & Emerging Trends* (2nd edn, Edinburgh Scholarship Online 2015) <<https://doi.org/10.3366/edinburgh/9781845861018.003.0008>> accessed 18 June 2022.

¹¹³ *ibid*

¹¹⁴ *ibid*

¹¹⁵ *ibid*

¹¹⁶ *ibid*

after starting operations on UKCS, killing thirteen people.¹¹⁷ Investigations revealed that poor regulatory framework was a major causative factor.¹¹⁸

The framework was based on the contractual relationship existing from the Minister's powers to grant licenses.¹¹⁹ Thus, the Minister lacked regulatory powers, powers to investigate, compel witnesses and administer oath. The principle of privity of contract was also restraining.¹²⁰

Licensees were to comply with the Minister's instructions regarding worker's safety, health and welfare.¹²¹ One of such instructions was that licensees comply with Part VIII of the Institute of Petroleum Model Code of Safe Practice in the Petroleum Industry (IP Code).¹²² The Sea Gem Inquiry report revealed that majority of the deaths were caused by strict adherence to the IP code which prescribed inadequate emergency responses.¹²³

The report contained recommendations which led to the adoption of prescriptive regulations.¹²⁴ Consequently, the Mineral Workings (Offshore Installations) Act 1971 and regulations made pursuant to it were passed. The regulator, Petroleum Engineering Division (PED) of the Department of Energy (DEn) had responsibility to develop and enforce safety regulations as well as grant petroleum licenses.¹²⁵ This raised suspicions of conflicting interests which was criticised by the government-sponsored committee led by Lord Robens.¹²⁶

3.2.2 The Robens Committee

The Robens Committee advised against the prescriptive approach, stating that it had the tendency to portray safety matters as government responsibility rather than an individual matter; to produce irrelevant laws; create multiple regulators; to lead to a proliferation of health and safety laws; to result

¹¹⁷ Carson W.G., 'The Other Price of Britain's Oil: Regulating Safety on Offshore Oil Installations in the British Sector of the North Sea.' (1980) 4(3) *Contemporary Crises* <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF00728253>> accessed 8 June 2022

¹¹⁸ John Paterson, 'The Significance of Regulatory Orientation in Occupational Health and Safety Offshore' (2011) 38(2) *Boston College Environmental Affairs Law Review* <<https://lawdigitalcommons.bc.edu/ealr/vol38/iss2/8>> accessed 8 July 2022

¹¹⁹ *ibid*

¹²⁰ Carson (n 117).

¹²¹ Paterson 'Health and Safety at Work Offshore' (n 112) 287.

¹²² Carson (n 117).

¹²³ Paterson 'Health and Safety at Work Offshore' (n 112) 287

¹²⁴ Ministry of Power, Report of the inquiry into the causes of the accident to the drilling rig Sea Gem (Cmd 3409) para 10.1

¹²⁵ P J Walmsley, 'The role of the Department of Energy in petroleum exploration of the United Kingdom' (1983) 12(1) *Geological Society Publications* <<https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.1983.012.01.02>> accessed 18 July 2022

¹²⁶ Paterson, 'Health and Safety at Work Offshore' (n 112)

in an incoherent national approach to health and safety.¹²⁷ The Robens Committee called for a “more effective self-regulation.”¹²⁸ The recommendations in the Committee’s report led to the passing of the Health and Safety at Work Act 1974 which adopted the non-prescriptive approach.¹²⁹ Although this Act did not apply offshore, it had impact on the industry in later years.¹³⁰

In 1977, the Ekofisk Bravo blowout occurred on the Norwegian sector of the North Sea, and again, UK convened a committee under the chairmanship of Dr J H Burgoyne to scrutinise its offshore safety regime.¹³¹

3.2.3 The Burgoyne Committee

The Committee made findings similar to the Sea Gem Inquiry but departed in advocating against the prescriptive regime.¹³² The Committee proposed objective-setting laws,¹³³ a single regulatory authority¹³⁴ and non-mandatory standards.¹³⁵ Unfortunately, there was “virtually no progress towards the creation of new goal-setting regulations since the publication of the Committee’s report.”¹³⁶

3.2.4 The Piper Alpha Disaster and Lord Cullen’s Report

On July 6, 1988, the Piper Alpha Oil production platform was almost entirely consumed by fire due to a series of explosions.¹³⁷ This disaster claimed the lives of 167 men, which is, so far, the worst offshore disaster in terms of deaths.¹³⁸ A senior Scottish judge, Lord Cullen, chaired a committee which investigated the disaster.¹³⁹ Lord Cullen made 106 recommendations towards improving the regime, including:

1. The establishment of a detailed safety case regime which requires operators to demonstrate the safety management system of their companies
2. That regulations should not be restrictive by imposing solutions but should set objectives
3. That guidance notes be non-mandatory where practicable
4. A single regulatory body for offshore operations safety

¹²⁷ Alfred Robens and others, *Safety and Health at Work: Report of the Committee 1970-72* (Cmd 5034)

¹²⁸ *ibid.*

¹²⁹ Paterson, ‘The Significance of Regulatory Orientation in Occupational Health and Safety Offshore’ (n 118)

¹³⁰ *ibid.*

¹³¹ Paterson, ‘Health and Safety at Work Offshore’ (n 112)

¹³² *ibid.*

¹³³ J.H Burgoyne, *Offshore Safety: Report of the Committee* (Cmd 7866)

¹³⁴ *ibid.*

¹³⁵ *ibid.*

¹³⁶ HC Deb 7 March 1991, col 484

¹³⁷ William Douglas Cullen, *The Public Inquiry into the Piper Alpha Disaster*, vol 1 (H.M.S.O. 1990)

¹³⁸ *ibid.*

¹³⁹ *ibid.*

5. The separation of safety regulatory and revenue maximising functions
6. Workforce inclusion in safety management¹⁴⁰

3.2.5 Safety Case Approach

The UK government accepted all of Cullen's recommendations.¹⁴¹ This reflected in the establishment of a single regulator, HSE, with sole responsibility for offshore safety, and the enactment of the Offshore Safety Act 1992 which extended the Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974 offshore.¹⁴² This new act repealed regulations made pursuant to the Mineral Workings (Offshore Installations) Act 1971 and provided for new regulations adopting the goal-setting approach.¹⁴³

The Offshore Installations (Safety Representatives and Safety Committees) Regulations 1989 and Offshore Installations (Safety Case) Regulations 1992 established the safety case approach and introduced safety representations and workforce inclusion in safety management, respectively. By this, operators had the duty to develop an internal safety system and demonstrate this to the regulator through the safety case. The safety case was required to be resubmitted every three years and reaccepted by the regulator.

The 1992 Safety Case regulations and the supporting goal setting regulations made tremendous differences in the UK's regime. However, the 1992 regulations created an excessive bureaucratic atmosphere. Also, it was observed that the safety cases resubmitted every three were downgraded with each resubmission. The 1992 regulations were, therefore, updated by the 2005 regulations which required a five-year thorough review conditional on the acceptance of the HSE, and the involvement of the workforce in not just preparation of the safety case but also in its review and revision, thus increasing workforce engagement.

3.2.6 The Offshore Installations (Offshore Safety Directive) (Safety Case Etc.) Regulations 2015

Following the Deepwater Horizon incident on the Gulf of Mexico in April 2010, the European Commission (EC) through its communication 'Facing the Challenge of The Safety of Offshore Oil

¹⁴⁰ Cullen (n 137)

¹⁴¹ Charles Woolfson, John Foster, and Matthias Beck, *Paying for the Piper: Capital and Labour in Britain's Offshore Oil Industry* (Mansell, 1996)

¹⁴² *ibid.*

¹⁴³ *ibid.*

and Gas Activities¹⁴⁴ submitted that the offshore framework in Europe was inadequate.¹⁴⁵ As a result, the EC adopted the Offshore Directive¹⁴⁶ to reduce the occurrence of major accidents in the offshore industry and limit their consequences. About this time there was a blowout of well G4 on the Elgin Wellhead Platform.¹⁴⁷ With the blowout investigations, findings of the Maitland Review and the EU Directive, UK's HSE by the Offshore Installations (Offshore Safety Directive) (Safety Case etc.) Regulations 2015 which replaced the 1995 version introduced improvements to UK's regime including:

1. The establishment of Offshore Major Accident Regulator (OMAR) through a partnership between the Health and Safety Executive (HSE) and Offshore Petroleum Regulator for Environment & Decommissioning (part of the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS)).¹⁴⁸
2. Integration of environmental concerns into safety management through Safety and Environmental Management System (SEMS).¹⁴⁹
3. Increased workforce engagement in entire safety management.¹⁵⁰
4. Introduction of Corporate Major Accident Prevention Policy (CMAPP) for body corporates or unincorporates to show how major accidents will be managed.¹⁵¹

Today, UK'S regime is based on the safety case approach, non-prescriptive regulations and non-mandatory guidelines.

¹⁴⁴ Published on 13 October 2010

¹⁴⁵ HSE, 'Offshore Directive: The Safety of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations' (HSE) <<https://www.hse.gov.uk/offshore/directive.htm>> accessed 21 July 2022

¹⁴⁶ Directive 2013/30/EU of 12 June 2013 on Safety of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations and amending Directive 2004/35/EC

¹⁴⁷ HSE, 'The Elgin Wellhead Platform blowout 25 March 2012' (HSE, 2012) <<https://www.hse.gov.uk/offshore/elgin.pdf>> accessed 21 July 2022

¹⁴⁸ Initially Offshore Safety Directive Regulator (OSDR), see HSE, 'Offshore Major Accident Regulator (OMAR)' <<https://www.hse.gov.uk/omar/index.htm>> accessed 21 July 2022

¹⁴⁹ Offshore Installations (Offshore Safety Directive) (Safety Case etc.) Regulations 2015, reg 8

¹⁵⁰ *ibid*, schs 6(4), 7(4), 8(3)

¹⁵¹ *ibid*, reg 7

3.3 Offshore Safety Regime of The United States of America

3.3.1 Pre-Macondo Disaster

The US Outer Continental Shelf Lands Act (OCSLA)¹⁵² is the principal legislation governing offshore petroleum industry in the U.S.¹⁵³ OCSLA requires companies holding offshore leases or permits to protect the health and safety of their employees by complying with health and safety regulations.¹⁵⁴ OCSLA authorises the U.S. Department of the Interior (DOI) and the U.S. Coast Guard(CG) to make and enforce regulations to govern offshore activities.¹⁵⁵ It confers administrative duties on DOI to manage offshore petroleum resources and balance resource development objectives with the protection of human, marine and coastal environments.¹⁵⁶ It also authorises the DOI and CG to enforce regulations, and carry out scheduled and unscheduled on-site inspections of OCS sites and facilities, and to investigate and report incidents of death, serious injury, fire, and major oil spills exceeding 200 barrels in a 30-day period.¹⁵⁷ These inspections involve the use of checklists of potential incidents of noncompliance (PINCs) comprising a list of yes and no questions relating to regulations.¹⁵⁸ Noncompliance attracts sanctions depending on severity and frequency.¹⁵⁹ Thus, US regime was highly prescriptive and command-and-control based.¹⁶⁰ The DOI exercises some of its regulatory duties through subsidiary bodies, one of which was the Mineral Management Service (MMS), which, until 2010, DOI delegated its responsibilities over offshore energy to.¹⁶¹ MMS had three main administrative roles:

- i. evaluating, planning, and leasing offshore oil and gas resources;
- ii. implementing environmental and safety regulations; and
- iii. collecting royalties and managing revenue from energy activities.¹⁶²

¹⁵² Government of the United States, Outer Continental Shelf Lands Act, Public Law 212, Ch. 345, 67 Stat. 462, 43 U.S.C. 1331-1356a

¹⁵³ Jennifer Dagg and others, 'Comparing the Offshore Regulatory Regimes of the Canadian Arctic, the U.S., the U.K., Greenland and Norway' (Pembina Institute, 2011) <<https://www.pembina.org/reports/comparing-offshore-oil-and-gas-regulations.pdf>> accessed 12 June 2022.

¹⁵⁴ Michael Baram, 'The U.S. Regulatory Regime for Preventing Major Accidents in Offshore Operations' in Preben Hempel Lindøe, Michael Baram and Ortwin Renn, *Risk Governance of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations* (Cambridge University Press 2013).

¹⁵⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁵⁶ Dagg (n 153)

¹⁵⁷ Baram (n 154)

¹⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

¹⁶¹ *Ibid.*

¹⁶² *ibid.*

The US Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) which regulates onshore operation lacks statutory authority over offshore operations,¹⁶³ by virtue of OCSLA and Occupational Safety and Health Act of 1970.¹⁶⁴ OSHA has publicly maintained this stance even during the Macondo incidence,¹⁶⁵ when its expertise was greatly needed.¹⁶⁶

3.3.2 Macondo Disaster

For about forty (40) years,¹⁶⁷ there were no major accidents on the US Outer Continental Shelf (OCS).¹⁶⁸ There were, however, minor accidents and continuous disregard for worker's health and safety,¹⁶⁹ which were tolerated until April 2010, when Macondo drilling site on the US sector of the Gulf of Mexico exploded.¹⁷⁰ This killed eleven(11) workers, injured seventeen (17),¹⁷¹ and caused excessive discharge of about 40,000 barrels of oil per day for 87 days into the marine environment until a temporary cap was successfully placed.¹⁷² This is recorded as the worst ever offshore oil spill.¹⁷³ This disaster subjected the US regime to scrutiny.¹⁷⁴

3.3.3 Macondo Disaster Investigations

The National Commission on the Deepwater Horizon Accident revealed that a primary cause of the disaster was US faulty offshore regime.¹⁷⁵ OCSLA was criticised for its inflexible prescriptive regulatory style¹⁷⁶ which was unable to keep up with offshore technological advancement and

¹⁶³ OSHA, 'Worker Health and Safety from the Oil Rig to the Shoreline' (OSHA, 2010) <<https://www.osha.gov/news/testimonies/06232010>> accessed 12 June 2022

¹⁶⁴ 29 USC 651 et seq.

¹⁶⁵ OSHA 'Worker Health and Safety from the Oil Rig to the Shoreline' (n 163)

¹⁶⁶ Baram (n 154)

¹⁶⁷ After the blowout and spill of the Amoco Cadiz in 1969

¹⁶⁸ Baram (n 154)

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ Baram (n 154)

¹⁷¹ National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling, *Deep Water: The Gulf Oil Disaster and the Future of Offshore Drilling : Report to the President* (National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling 2011)

¹⁷² Baram (n 154)

¹⁷³ Bp, 'Deepwater Horizon Accident Investigation Report' (bp, 2010) <<https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/sustainability/issue-briefings/deepwater-horizon-accident-investigation-report.pdf>> accessed 20 June 2022.

¹⁷⁴ Preben Hempel Lindøe and others (eds.), 'Regulatory Regimes: Norway, United Kingdom, United States, and Australia' in Preben Hempel Lindøe, Michael Baram and Ortwin Renn, *Risk Governance of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations* (Cambridge University Press 2013).

¹⁷⁵ Ibiere Jumbo and Ngozi Chinwa Ole, 'A Critical Analysis of the Nigerian Offshore Oil Risk Governance Regime (Post Macondo)' (2019) 3(3) African Journal of International Energy and Environmental Law <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3514484>> accessed 5 July 2022

¹⁷⁶ National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling (n 171)

emerging risks of operations in the Deepwater.¹⁷⁷ The CG confessed during investigations that the regulations were not as rigorous as should have been as the rig was examined nine times before the accident with no major faults found.¹⁷⁸

Furthermore, the Commission stated that OCSLA did not prioritise risk governance over revenue generation.¹⁷⁹ For example, OCSLA requires licensees to use the best available and safest technologies for offshore operations to the economically feasible extent.¹⁸⁰ The ‘economically feasible’ caveat is reported to have occasioned a compromise in the safety standards of the industry.¹⁸¹ Also, contrary to MMS’ assertion that the disaster was unforeseeable, evidence exists that shows that there were signs of impending disaster which MMS ignored because it was economically convenient to.¹⁸² This was compounded by the fact that MMS lacked independence and was given the twofold responsibility of safety regulation and revenue maximisation.¹⁸³ It was therefore concluded that MMS did not ‘have the incentive to make sound ... enforcement decisions that might conflict with its revenue-raising goals.’¹⁸⁴

The Committee resolved that the regulators lacked capacity as they could not identify the dangers presented by several warnings of the imminent blowout¹⁸⁵ by making use of real time data, information on incidents, near misses and lessons learned worldwide to adjust practices and standards.¹⁸⁶

MMS was also criticised for adopting American Petroleum Institute(API) private standards and recommended practices as mandatory and enforceable rules.¹⁸⁷ This meant that API determined the

¹⁷⁷ Baram (n 154)

¹⁷⁸ National Research Council and others, *Macondo Well Deepwater Horizon Blowout: Lessons for Improving Offshore Drilling Safety* (National Academies Press 2012)

¹⁷⁹ Robert L. Glicksman, ‘Regulatory Blowout: How Regulatory Failures Made the BP Disaster Possible, and How the System Can Be Fixed to Avoid a Recurrence’ (2010) 608 *GW Law Faculty Publications & Other Works* <https://scholarship.law.gwu.edu/faculty_publications/608> accessed 18 June 2022

¹⁸⁰ OCSLA, s 1347(b)

¹⁸¹ C. Carrigan, ‘Captured by Disaster: Reinterpreting Regulatory Behaviour in the Shadow of the Gulf Oil Spill’ in David Carpenter and David A Moss (eds), *Preventing Regulatory Capture* (Cambridge University Press 2014) 240.

¹⁸² Mark Clayton, ‘Studies Suggest that MMS knew that Blowout had Critical Flaws’ (CSMonitor, 2010) <<https://www.csmonitor.com/USA/2010/0617/Studies-suggest-MMS-knew-blowout-preventers-had-critical-flaws>> accessed 26 July 2022.

¹⁸³ Heidi Gorovitz Robertson, ‘Applying Some Lessons from the Gulf Oil Spill to Hydraulic Fracturing’ (2013) 63 *Case W. Rsr. L Rev* 1279 <<https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/caselrev/vol63/iss4/12>> accessed 27 July 2022

¹⁸⁴ *ibid.*

¹⁸⁵ Jeffery Ray, ‘Offshore Safety and Environmental Regimes: A Post-Macondo Comparative Analysis of the United States and United Kingdom’ (2013) *SSRN Electronic Journal* <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2370709>> accessed 25 July 2022

¹⁸⁶ National Research Council and others (n 178)

¹⁸⁷ Baram (n 154)

rate at which risks were reduced in the industry, which lagged at the time of the 2010 disaster.¹⁸⁸ Also, such private standards were agreed upon privately without the involvement of the workforce and stakeholders who have genuine personal concerns and knowledge about the work.¹⁸⁹ Likewise, OCSLA vested no participatory rights on offshore workers in the safety management of industry.¹⁹⁰

There were also jurisdictional issues amongst the regulatory agencies which occasioned uncoordinated collaboration on offshore regulation.¹⁹¹

3.3.4 Post-Macondo Disaster Regulatory Reform

Following the incident, US began regulatory reforms. Initially, DOI terminated MMS, created the Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, Regulation and Enforcement (BOEMRE)¹⁹² and temporarily vested on it all responsibilities previously borne by MMS.¹⁹³ The following year, DOI transferred BOEMRE roles to two newly created organisations, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM) and Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement (BSEE).¹⁹⁴ BOEM is responsible for the development of OCS energy and mineral resources in an environmentally and economically responsible way.¹⁹⁵ BSEE, on the other hand, is responsible for promoting safety and environmental protection related to the offshore energy industry on the US OCS.¹⁹⁶ Other agencies such as the CG still play important regulatory roles.¹⁹⁷

Furthermore, DOI introduced the Safety and Environmental Management System (SEMS).¹⁹⁸ US SEMS requires companies to develop, implement and manage a safety and environmental system

¹⁸⁸ Ibid.

¹⁸⁹ Ibid.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid.

¹⁹¹ Ibid.

¹⁹² U.S. Department of the Interior, 'Reorganization of Offshore Energy Agencies' (DOI, 2011) <https://www.doi.gov/ocl/hearings/112/OffshoreEnergyAgenciesBromwich_071511> accessed 15 July 2022

¹⁹³ Ibid.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁹⁵ Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement, 'Organizational History' (BSEE) < [https://www.bsee.gov/about-bsee/our-organization/organizational-history#:~:text=The%20final%20stage%20of%20the,Ocean%20Energy%20Management%20\(BOEM.\)](https://www.bsee.gov/about-bsee/our-organization/organizational-history#:~:text=The%20final%20stage%20of%20the,Ocean%20Energy%20Management%20(BOEM.))> accessed 17 July 2022

¹⁹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁹⁷ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, *Strengthening the Safety Culture of the Offshore Oil and Gas Industry* (The National Academies Press 2016) <<https://doi.org/10.17226/23524>> accessed 20 July 2022

¹⁹⁸ Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement, 'Safety and Environmental Management Systems – SEMS' (BSEE) <<https://www.bsee.gov/reporting-and-prevention/safety-and-environmental-management-systems>> accessed 27 July 2022

according to the American Petroleum Institute's (API's) Recommended Practice 75 for Development of a Safety and Environmental Management Program for Offshore Operations and Facilities.¹⁹⁹

In 2013, BSEE published an updated SEMS rule²⁰⁰ which introduced:

- a) A clearly define ultimate work authority for safety and decision making at any given time;
- b) Enhanced employee participation in the management system;
- c) An established system for reporting to BSEE unsafe working conditions, dangers and violations of safety requirements;
- d) A requirement that workers who witness imminent risk stop work immediately;
- e) Auditing by accredited and independent third parties; and
- f) Additional requirements for conducting a job safety analysis.

In 2015, BSEE launched a voluntary near-miss reporting program called SafeOCS.²⁰¹

Despite SEMS, US regime is still largely prescriptive.²⁰²

3.4 Conclusion

This chapter examined the offshore regimes of UK and US. It revealed that regulatory reforms occurred in both jurisdictions following major offshore disasters. UK, particularly, demonstrated resilience in improving its regime, even when disasters occurred in jurisdictions other than its. US quit being headstrong in their faulty approach after the Macondo disaster. Although prescription still dominates their regime, the performance-based reforms introduced are praiseworthy.

These regimes will be comparatively analysed against the regime of Nigeria in the following chapter.

¹⁹⁹ National Research Council and others (n 178)

²⁰⁰ Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement, 'Safety and Environmental Management Systems – SEMS' (n 198)

²⁰¹ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²⁰² Dagg (n 153)

4. CHAPTER 4 - COMPARATIVE CASE STUDIES OF THE OFFSHORE REGIMES OF NIGERIA, UK AND US

4.1 Introduction

While there are no accurate records of offshore accidents, injuries and deaths in Nigeria, there is no basis to assume that such incidents do not occur. Even if they did not, there is no reason why any country should be reactive in regulating offshore safety.

Different offshore regimes exist. Chapters 2 and 3 considered the regimes of Nigeria, UK and US. These regimes, despite certain similarities, have inherently different features.

This chapter will carry out a comparative analysis of Nigeria's regime against those of UK and US on set criteria of legal framework, regulatory body and safety management system. This analysis is aimed at identifying the strengths and weaknesses of Nigeria's regime, as well as recognising threats to the effectiveness of the regime and opportunities for establishing a robust regulatory framework in Nigeria. Through this analysis, also, it will be determined how far Nigeria's newly enacted Petroleum Industry Act 2021 has launched Nigeria into a safer and sustainable regime.

4.2 Legal Frameworks and Regulatory Approaches

Offshore regulatory approaches reflect in the legal framework of a country. These approaches are usually prescriptive or command-and-control, goal-setting or performance based or hybrid approach.

As discussed in chapter 3, UK's framework comprised of prescriptive rules until the 1990s when goal-setting regulations and non-mandatory guidance notes were adopted pursuant to Lord Cullen's recommendations.²⁰³ Similarly, US began and continued with prescriptive rules for almost half a century until 2010 when after the Macondo disaster, it adopted some performance-based approaches.²⁰⁴ Nonetheless, the US has retained its prescriptive rules and mandatory standards²⁰⁵ and thus implements a hybrid approach.²⁰⁶

Nigeria, on the other hand, has since inception of its offshore petroleum industry implemented the prescriptive approach. The Risk-Based Inspections Guidelines 2020 which adopts non-prescriptive

²⁰³ By virtue of the Offshore Safety Act 1992 (1992 chapter 15)

²⁰⁴ Through Safety and Environmental Management Systems (SEMS).

²⁰⁵ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²⁰⁶ Muhammad Zulfarnain, 'Regulations Governing Offshore Oil and Gas Operations' (2017) Encyclopedia of Maritime and Offshore Engineering <<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118476406.emoe422>> accessed 20 July 2022

style contains a caveat that accords superiority to the prescriptive provisions of the Mineral Oils (Safety) Regulations under which it was issued, itself only an alternative to it.²⁰⁷ The rest of the guidelines prescribe mandatory standards including those of American Petroleum Institute, American National Standards Institute, American Society of Mechanical Engineers and National Association of Corrosion Engineers.

Despite the advantages of the prescriptive approach to introduce certainty and ease regulation for authorities, its disadvantages, amplified by several authors²⁰⁸ and exemplified in the UK and US regimes, are overwhelming.²⁰⁹

Firstly, prescriptive rules inhibit “industry’s capacity for innovation and technological change.”²¹⁰ They have the tendency to produce a ‘compliance mentality’²¹¹ and reduce operators’ awareness to emerging hazards.²¹² The inflexibility of prescriptive rules hinders opportunities for operators to develop better approaches to safety as they have no incentive to do more than the law requires.²¹³ This reduces safety to a ‘reactive role in relation to technological advances.’²¹⁴ It is recorded that this was a contributory factor to the Piper Alpha disaster in the US.²¹⁵ The US CG even confessed during investigations that the regulations were not robust enough to cater for the Deepwater drilling operations and technology.²¹⁶

Secondly, the prescriptive approach presents a rigid one-size-fits-all rules for companies in the industry without regard to individual operational and structural differences which may resist their effectiveness.²¹⁷

²⁰⁷ Risk Based Inspections Guidelines 2020, s 2

²⁰⁸ As referenced in this sub-chapter

²⁰⁹ Dagg (n 153)

²¹⁰ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²¹¹ Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement, ‘Safety and Environmental Management Systems – SEMS’ (BSEE) < <https://www.bsee.gov/reporting-and-prevention/safety-and-environmental-management-systems> > accessed 27 July 2022

²¹² Yuan Yang, ‘Reforming Health, Safety, and Environmental Regulation for Offshore Operations in China: Risk and Resilience Approaches?’ (2019) *Sustainability* 11(9) <<https://doi.org/10.3390/su11092608>> accessed 13 July 2022

²¹³ Preben Hempel Lindøe, Michael Baram and Ortwin Renn, *Risk Governance of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations* (Cambridge University Press 2013)

²¹⁴ John Paterson, ‘Behind the Mask: Regulating Health and Safety in Britain’s Offshore Oil and Gas Industry’ (2017)

²¹⁵ Bp, ‘Deepwater Horizon Accident Investigation Report’ (n 173)

²¹⁶ National Research Council and others (n 178)

²¹⁷ Lindøe (n 213)

Thirdly, the mandate to comply to the letters of the law²¹⁸ presents a loophole which can be taken advantage of by companies who when apprehended for poor practices, can easily use strict compliance as a defence, especially in cases of negligence.²¹⁹

Fourthly, prescriptive rules are insufficient by reason of their being made by the government who are not directly engaged in offshore operations, and the inability of the rules to cover every aspect of the industry.²²⁰

According to World Economic Forum ‘technological developments combined with economic, social and environmental shifts ... rapidly make ... prescriptive approaches outdated,’²²¹ and outdated laws are unproductive. Despite the new Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) in Nigeria, regulations which existed at the infancy of Nigeria’s offshore operations still regulate the industry. The Act, by saving these regulations, did nothing to introduce recent and more relevant regulations. The fines for noncompliance, for example, do not convey the deterrent effect that they ought to. The only amendments to the regulations introduced by the Act concern prices of oil mining and oil prospecting licences,²²² and of royalties to be paid for produced petroleum resources.²²³ This suggests prioritization of revenue maximisation over safety regulations by the government.

Additionally, subjecting offshore operations to good oil field practice and mandatory foreign codes can be counterproductive. Good oil field practice is ambiguous and lacks definite thresholds.²²⁴ The foreign codes, such as those of API, have counterproductive and conflicting tendencies due to the different legal and environmental terrains of Nigeria and America.²²⁵ This is compounded by the fact that the regulations provide no guidance as to the reconciliation of such conflicts if they occur.

²¹⁸ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²¹⁹ Richard C. Ausness, The Case for a "Strong" Regulatory Compliance Defense, 55 Md. L. Rev. 1210 (1996)

²²⁰ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²²¹ https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Agile_Regulation_for_the_Fourth_Industrial_Revolution_2020.pdf World Economic Reform, ‘Agile Regulation for the Fourth Industrial Revolution: A Toolkit for Regulators’ (2020) <[WEF Agile Regulation for the Fourth Industrial Revolution 2020.pdf \(weforum.org\)](https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Agile_Regulation_for_the_Fourth_Industrial_Revolution_2020.pdf)> accessed 17 July 2022

²²² Petroleum (Drilling and Production) (Amendment) Regulations, 2019

²²³ Petroleum (Drilling & Production) (Amendments) Regulations 2020

²²⁴ Mohammed Al-Najjar and A F M Maniruzzaman, ‘The Legal, Environmental and Social Prospects of the Term ‘Good Oilfield Practice’ within the Onshore Upstream Oil Industry: Law in the Making?’ (2020) <[OGEL ESG MohammedAl Najjar AFMManiruzzaman fnl.pdf \(port.ac.uk\)](#)> accessed 9 August 2022

²²⁵ The Director-General of Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON), Mr Osita Aboloma noted in 2019 concerning the adoption of 10 American Petroleum Institute (API) standards that “In adopting international standards we must ensure that the standards are not in conflict with our statutory regulatory requirements... Special consideration should be on environmental factors, economic considerations, security of products, national interest and most of all, global best practices.” See The Guardian, ‘NAN, SON adopts American standards to boost oil, gas industry’ (The Guardian, 2019)

Unfortunately, it is onerous to appraise the success of these mandatory standards in the history of Nigeria's offshore petroleum industry because of the paucity of existing literature on the subject and the unavailability of public database and investigations of offshore activities. However, it does not take rocket science to recognise that the regulations, considering technological advancements and social realities today, are obsolete and inadequate to secure the safety of offshore workers.

On the other hand, since the goal-setting approach, adopted by UK, specifies the goal/objective to be achieved, it promotes the continuous development of risk management.²²⁶ It provides for almost everything that the prescriptive approach is not; flexible, relevant, up-to-date, adaptable, progressive and engaging. Non-mandatory and non-prescriptive rules are more capable of accommodating technological changes and thus, challenge operators to innovate better methods of ensuring safety.²²⁷ Although goals set without specific standards may pose a difficulty to effective regulation and risk underperformance, this can be curbed by establishing tripartite consultation in safety management systems of companies. This way, a representative of each stakeholder (the government, the industry and the workers) is involved in effective and continuous safety regulation.²²⁸ Adopting a goal setting approach will establish a more sustainable safety regime for Nigeria as it has for UK.

4.3 Regulatory Bodies

Previously, UK's PED had responsibility over offshore safety as well as revenue maximisation from petroleum activities.²²⁹ This was criticised by the Lord Robens' and Lord Cullen's committees due to conflicting interests. Eventually, UK separated these roles by establishing the HSE as regulator over offshore safety solely.²³⁰ Today, the North Sea Transition Authority is UK's authority for revenue

< [SON adopts American standards to boost oil, gas industry | The Guardian Nigeria News - Nigeria and World News — Nigeria — The Guardian Nigeria News – Nigeria and World News](#) > accessed 20 July 2022

²²⁶ Yang (n 212)

²²⁷ Neil Gunningham, 'Types of Regulatory Approaches' (1997) <[Page Title \(tripod.com\)](#)> accessed 12 July 2022

²²⁸ Ibid.

²²⁹ P. J. Walmsley (n 125)

²³⁰ John Paterson, 'Health and Safety Regulation on the UK Continental Shelf: Evolution and Future Prospects' in Preben Hempel Lindøe, Michael Baram and Ortwin Renn (eds), *Risk Governance of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations* (2nd edn, Cambridge University Press 2013) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/risk-governance-of-offshore-oil-and-gas-operations/health-and-safety-regulation-on-the-uk-continental-shelf/5F0DA92D165B6A180AE55801669D68EB>> accessed 18 June 2022.

maximisation²³¹ while Offshore Major Accident Regulator (OMAR) is responsible for safety regulation.²³²

Similarly, following reports of MMS conflicting interests,²³³ US separated these roles by establishing BOEM for revenue maximisation²³⁴ and BSEE for promoting safety.²³⁵

In Nigeria however, this twofold responsibility remains a feature. This is so despite the new Act and its creation of a new regulator, Nigeria Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC). Unlike its predecessor, NUPRC is an independent regulator but, the value of this independence is threatened by the retained twofold responsibility.

NUPRC has the objectives to achieve optimal government revenues;²³⁶ and to promote healthy, safe conduct of offshore operations in an environmentally acceptable and sustainable manner.²³⁷ Petroleum is the backbone of the Nigerian economy representing about 90% of its revenue.²³⁸ Its lucrateness has the tendency to nurture bias in favour of revenue maximisation and at the detriment of safety regulation. This was evident in the past regulator,²³⁹ and remains threatening to the sustainability of Nigeria's regime. Objectivity in offshore safety regulation must not only be done but must be seen to be done by the separation of these roles. This is a necessary feature for a robust regime as exemplified by UK and US.

4.4 Safety Management Systems and workforce Involvement

Following Lord Cullen's recommendations UK also adopted its safety case regime.²⁴⁰ This introduced tripartite consultation which enables dialogue and cooperation between the regulator, operators and workers' representatives towards building and maintaining a strong safety culture.²⁴¹ Additionally,

²³¹ GOV.UK, 'North Sea Transition Authority' (GOV.UK) <[North Sea Transition Authority - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](http://www.gov.uk)> accessed 11 July 2022

²³² HSE, 'Offshore Major Accident Regulator (OMAR)' (HSE) <[Offshore Major Accident Regulator \(OMAR\) \(hse.gov.uk\)](http://hse.gov.uk)> accessed 10 July 2022

²³³ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (n 197)

²³⁴ U.S. Department of the Interior, 'Reorganization of Offshore Energy Agencies' (DOI, 2011) <[Reorganization of Offshore Energy Agencies | U.S. Department of the Interior \(doi.gov\)](http://doi.gov)> accessed 15 July 2022

²³⁵ *ibid.*

²³⁶ Petroleum Industry Act, s 6(c)

²³⁷ *Ibid*, s 6(d)

²³⁸ Odularu, Gbadebo. (2008). Crude Oil and the Nigerian Economic Performance. Oil and Gas Business. [PDF\) Crude Oil and the Nigerian Economic Performance \(researchgate.net\)](https://www.researchgate.net)

²³⁹ Ugo Nwokeji (n 103)

²⁴⁰ The Offshore Installations (Safety Case) Regulations 1992.

²⁴¹ Safety Case Directive, sch 2

UK's Offshore Installations (Safety Representatives and Safety Committees) Regulations 1989 make it mandatory for workers to be given the opportunity to select safety representatives.²⁴²

US does not operate a safety case regime. It introduced a Safety and Environment Management System which was in 2013 amended to enhance workers involvement in the Safety and Environment Management System.²⁴³

Laudably, Nigeria operates a safety case regime. Like the safety case of UK, it requires the establishment of a safety management system,²⁴⁴ the submission, review, approval and verification of a safety case. However, unlike in the safety management system of UK and US, Nigeria limits the scope for workforce involvement.

In Nigeria, workers are only required to be involved in the development the safety case.²⁴⁵ In UK and US this involvement is required in all stages of the system. This is a weakness in Nigeria's regime that must be addressed.

No employer or contractor can effectively ensure safety without cooperating with employees.²⁴⁶ This is because workers have the most direct contact with the risks and hazards of offshore operations, thus, know the problems first-hand.²⁴⁷ Worker's involvement and representation is an opportunity to foster a safety culture within the industry.²⁴⁸ Their involvement in safety regulations should not be minimised. This conclusion was endorsed by the international Labour Organisation at the World Day for Safety and Health at Work 2022.²⁴⁹ UK's and Norway's²⁵⁰ robust regimes enjoy the benefits of enhanced workforce involvement, and so should Nigeria's.

²⁴² Offshore Installations (Safety Representatives and Safety Committees) Regulations 1989, s 4

²⁴³ Oil and Gas and Sulphur Operations on the Outer Continental Shelf-Increased Safety Measures for Energy Development on the Outer Continental Shelf, § 250.1932

²⁴⁴ Safety and Environment Management System in UK and US incorporates environmental aspects in their system - SEMS

²⁴⁵ Safety Case Guidelines 2020, ss 5.3 and 5.4

²⁴⁶ HSE, 'Play Your Part' (HSE) < [Play your part! How offshore workers can help improve health and safety \(hse.gov.uk\)](https://www.hse.gov.uk/playyourpart/)> accessed 29 July 2022

²⁴⁷ *ibid.*

²⁴⁸ *ibid.*

²⁴⁹ *ibid.*

²⁵⁰ Knut Kaasen, Safety Regulation on the Norwegian Continental Shelf, in Risk Governance of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations, 166 (Preben Hempel Lindøe et al. eds., 2014)

A summary of the different features of the US, UK and Nigeria regimes is presented below:

	Jurisdiction	Regulatory Approach	Safety Regulator	Safety Management System	Workers' Involvement
1	United Kingdom	Performance based approach comprising goal-setting rules, non-mandatory guidelines, the safety case regime, the safety and environment management system	OMAR with responsibility for safety regulation	Safety case regime including Safety and Environment Management System	Enhanced and mandatory workforce involvement and representation by elected representatives in all stages of safety management
2	United States of America	hybrid approach of prescriptive as well as performance based by the introduction of Safety and Environmental Management Systems (SEMS).	BSEE with the responsibility for safety regulation	Safety and environment management system integrated with prescriptive and mandatory standard	Enhanced and mandatory workforce involvement in all stages of the SEMS
3	Nigeria	Hybrid approach of prescription majorly, and safety case regime	NUPRC with two-fold responsibility of revenue maximisation and safety regulation	Safety Case Regime including Safety Management System, prescriptive rules and mandatory standards	Limited workforce involvement in the development of safety case only

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter analysed the regulatory regime of Nigeria against those of UK and US. The differences and similarities between these regimes were highlighted on the criteria of legal framework, regulatory approach, regulatory body, and safety management system.

While Nigeria and US adopt a hybrid regulatory approach, UK adopts a performance-based and goal-setting approach. The strengths and weaknesses of the prescriptive and goal-setting approaches were explored.

Concerning regulatory body, the chapter revealed that Nigeria, unlike the other regimes, has a regulator with twofold responsibilities of safety regulation and revenue maximisation. The experiences of UK and US exposed the shortcomings of this structure and so it is advisable for Nigeria to detach these roles.

This chapter also revealed the different levels of workforce involvement in the regimes, with the highest involvement being in UK, followed by US and then Nigeria. Nigeria limits workforce engagement in safety regulation.

Upon these, this chapter revealed that Nigeria's regime is fortified by the establishment of an independent regulator and a safety case regime. But is weakened by its prescriptive approach, mandatory standards, regulator with conflicting duties and limited workforce involvement.

There is no best regulatory approach, neither is there a one-size-fits-all model.²⁵¹ UK's experience has shown that there is always room for improvement, and any opportunity to improve must be seized. A total transplant of one country's regime to another may be counterproductive but aspects of a country's regime that can be adapted and finetuned to suit a different country's system for improved safety will be highly beneficial. Through the law-making powers vested by the Act on the regulator, Nigeria can adopt best practices learned from these mature regimes as would be recommended in the next chapter.

²⁵¹ Robert Baldwin, Martin Cave, Martin Lodge (eds) *The Oxford Handbook of Regulation* (Oxford University Press 2010)

*No doubt, the offshore industry is inherently risky, but even the riskiest industries can be made safer.*²⁵²

5. CHAPTER 5 – CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study began by establishing the relationship between occupational health and safety and sustainable development. It went on to explore the regulatory regimes of Nigeria, UK and US; their legislative framework, regulatory bodies and safety management systems. Accordingly, this study evaluated the robustness of Nigeria's regime against those of UK and US. The regimes of UK and US are more advanced than Nigeria's, having experienced disasters which not only tested their suitability but motivated them to develop safer regimes.

This work has contributed to knowledge about the impact of the new Petroleum Industry Act 2021 on offshore safety regulation, on which there is scant existing literature. Additionally, Contrary to existing literature that posits Nigeria's regime as completely prescriptive,²⁵³ this research reveals that performance-based approach (Safety Case) partly exists within Nigeria's regime.

By analysing Nigeria's regime against the regimes of UK and US, this work showed that Nigeria's regime is not as robust as it should be in order to attain social sustainability. The largely prescriptive regulatory approach, outdated laws, conflicting interests of the regulator and limited workforce involvement in Nigeria's regime are indicative. There is large room for improvement taking alone from the experiences of UK and US. It is no gainsaying that 'an ounce of prevention is better than a pound of cure.'²⁵⁴ Nigeria does not need to suffer disasters like Macondo or Piper Alpha before it establishes a safer regime.

NUPRC is on a mission to ensure sustainable development of Nigeria's Upstream Petroleum Resources... But an industry cannot achieve sustainable development where its workers are not safe. Based on these conclusions, Nigeria should take necessary reformatory steps as recommended in the next sub-chapter to establish a robust safety regime.

²⁵² National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling (n 171)

²⁵³ Jumbo (n 175)

²⁵⁴ Benjamin Franklin

*Continuous learning is the minimum requirement for success in any field.*²⁵⁵

5.2 Recommendations

The Petroleum Industry Act remains a viable tool to upgrade Nigeria's regime if the powers it confers on the regulators are continually employed to make relevant changes to create a safer regime. On this note, the regulations and guidelines should be amended to:

1. Adopt a proactive performance-based approach as the main regulatory model.
2. Eradicate prescriptive and mandatory rules by replacing them with goal-setting rules
3. Enhance workforce involvement and representation in the entire safety management system.
4. Mandate tripartite consultations for developing suitable standards for the industry
5. Detach from NUPRC the role of revenue maximisation or establish a new regulator with the sole responsibility of offshore safety regulation.
6. Convey a general theme of maintaining high standards of safety and prevention of accidents and harm to the overall wellbeing of offshore workers
7. Bring regulations and guidelines up to date in line with social realities

Additionally, the government should

8. Develop policy for the industry incorporating the precautionary and preventive principles as guiding principles in OHS
9. Direct investments to safety research and development towards promoting offshore safety
10. Establish a public database where records of accidents and near-misses are shared
11. Recruit and develop experienced and capable experts in the field.

Word count: 10,986 (Including footnotes)

²⁵⁵ Brian Tracy

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